

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. – First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. – Professor, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO.

Program Committee Members:

Formanov Sh. K. – Academician, AS of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan)

Aripov M. M. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Shadimetov Kh. M. – Professor, Tashkent State Technical University

Aloev R. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Khayotov A. R. – Professor, Institute of Mathematics, Academy of Sciences (Uzbekistan)

Khudoyberganov M. O. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Sharipov O. Sh. – NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Eshkuvvatov Z. K. – Professor, National Research University TIAME (Uzbekistan)

Kobulov A. V. – Professor, NUUz (Uzbekistan)

Mascagni M. – Professor, Florida State University (USA)

Li Y. – Professor, Old Dominion University (USA)

Gemma M. – Professor, Vice President of Waseda University (Japan)

Nishimura Shoji – Professor, Dean of Waseda University (Japan)

Hwang C. O. – Professor, Gwangju Institute of Science and Technology (Korea)

Seitov A. Zh. – Professor, UWED (Uzbekistan)

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. – Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. – Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Bakoev M. T. – Academic Director of the Tashkent Branch of MGIMO

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Seitov A. Zh. UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R.,
Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Optimal quadrature formulas in the space $W_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}$ of periodic functions

Qobilov Hojiakbar^{1,2}, Azamov Siroj¹

¹ *Tashkent State Transport University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan,*

² *Tashkent International University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

khoji1997@mail.ru

1. Introduction Numerical calculation of integrals of the highly oscillating integrals is one of the more critical problems on numerical analysis because such integrals are widely used in science and technology. The following types of the Fourier integrals are also examples of strongly oscillating integrals for sufficiently large ω :

$$I(\omega, \varphi) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i \omega x} \varphi(x) dx \quad (1)$$

It is known that the Fourier transforms are very important tools and they are used widely, in particular, in the problems of Computed Tomography (see, for instance [9]). Since in practice we have finite discrete values of a function, we have to approximately calculate the Fourier transforms. Therefore, one has to consider the problem of approximate calculation of the integral with the weight function $\exp(2\pi i \omega x)$. Initially, a formula for the numerical integration of the strongly oscillatory functions one of the non standard numerical integration methods was given by Filon [4].

Subsequently for integrals with different types of highly oscillating functions many special effective methods such as the Filon-type method, Clenshaw-Curtis-Filon type method, modified Clenshaw-Curtis method, Levin type methods, generalized quadrature rule, and Gauss-Laguerre quadrature are developed (see [2] for full details, for instance, [8,] and references therein).

Recently, in the work [7] author constructed optimal quadrature formulas for numerical calculation of Fourier integrals in the Sobolev space $L_2^{(m)}$ and in the Hilbert space $W_2^{m,m-1,m-2}$, and these formulas were applied to approximate reconstruction of Computed Tomography images. Compared with the optimal quadrature formulas in non-periodic case constructed in [6], the approximation formula for the periodic case constructed in the work [7] is much simpler, therefore it is easy to implement and it costs less computation even though both provide similar performances.

In various Hilbert and Banach spaces of periodic and non-periodic functions, optimal quadrature formulas have been constructed by many researchers for integral (1) with $\omega = 0$. The results for this case can be found, for instance, in the books [6, 9] and the literature in them. In particular, some recent results on optimal quadrature and interpolation formulas are obtained in the work [3].

In the work [5, pp. 119-142] weighted optimal quadrature and cubature formulas in the Sobolev space of periodic functions were constructed. In particular, one can get from

these results the optimal quadrature formulas for numerical calculation of the integral (1). For example, the practical use of these formulas which were constructed in the Hilbert spaces of non-periodic functions created difficulties in computational work.

Therefore, construction of new optimal quadrature formulas, which are simple in implementation, in various Hilbert spaces of periodic functions is very important. We note that we have constructed the optimal quadrature formula in the case $m = 2$ for integral (1) with $\omega = 0$ in the paper [10]. In the present work we get the results for $m \geq 3$.

Here, we solve the problem of construction of optimal quadrature formula in the Hilbert space $\widetilde{W}_2^{m,m-1,m-2}$ of periodic functions. In the book [9], the optimal quadrature formulas were constructed in the general case in the space of periodic functions, and it was proved that the coefficients of the formulas have the form $\tilde{C}_k = h$. Nevertheless the estimation of the error for the optimal formulas was not given. The main goal of the present work is to find the sharp upper bound for the error of the optimal quadrature formula constructed in the space $\widetilde{W}_2^{m,m-1,m-2}(0, 1]$ of periodic, real-valued functions.

We consider the Hilbert space $W_2^{m,m-1,m-2}(0, 1]$, $m \geq 3$ of non-periodic, real-valued functions $\varphi(x)$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, that $(m - 2)$ and order derivative is absolute continuous and m th order derivative (in the generalized sense) are square integrable, with the inner product

$$\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle_{W_2^{m,m-1,m-2}} = \int_0^1 \left(\varphi^{(m)}(x)\psi^{(m)}(x) + 2\varphi^{(m-1)}(x)\psi^{(m-1)}(x) + \varphi^{(m-2)}(x)\psi^{(m-2)}(x) \right) dx \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi, \psi \in W_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}(0, 1]$, and the corresponding norm of the function φ is defined as follows

$$\|\varphi\|_{W_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}} = \left(\int_0^1 \left((\varphi^{(m)}(x))^2 + 2(\varphi^{(m-1)}(x))^2 + (\varphi^{(m-2)}(x))^2 \right) dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Let us denote by $\widetilde{W}_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}(0, 1]$ the subspace of the space $W_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}(0, 1]$ consisting of real-valued, 1-periodic functions $\varphi(x)$, $x \in (0, 1]$.

In the present paper, we consider the Hilbert space $\widetilde{W}_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}(0, 1]$ of 1-periodic, real-valued functions. Notice that every element of the space satisfies the following condition of 1-periodicity

$$\varphi(x + \beta) = \varphi(x) \quad \text{for } x \in \mathbb{R} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

We consider a quadrature formula of the following form

$$\int_0^1 \varphi(x) dx \cong \sum_{k=1}^N C_k \varphi(x_k) \quad (3)$$

where $\varphi \in \widetilde{W}_2^{(m,m-1,m-2)}$, C_k are the coefficients of the quadrature formula and N is the number of nodes, $h = \frac{1}{N}$ and x_k ($0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_N \leq 1$) are nodes. Since quadrature

formula of the form (1) with equidistant nodes is optimal for the periodic functions class, we choose the nodes as $x_k = hk$ (see [9]).

The error of the quadrature formula (1) is given as follows

$$(\ell, \varphi) = \int_0^1 \varphi(x) dx - \sum_{k=1}^N C_k \varphi(hk) = \int_0^1 \left[\left(\varepsilon_{(0,1]}(x) - \sum_{k=1}^N C_k \delta(x - hk) \right) * \phi_0(x) \right] \varphi(x) dx, \quad (4)$$

where $h = \frac{1}{N}$, $\varepsilon_{(0,1]}(x)$ is the characteristic function of the interval $(0, 1]$, δ is the Dirac delta-function, $\phi_0(x) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x - h\beta)$, $*$ is the convolution operation and

$$\ell(x) = \left(\varepsilon_{(0,1]}(x) - \sum_{k=1}^N C_k \delta(x - hk) \right) * \phi_0(x) \quad (5)$$

and it is the periodic error functional of the quadrature formula (1).

The error (2) of the quadrature formula (1) is a linear functional in $\widetilde{W}_2^{(m, m-1, m-2)*}$. It should be noted that $\widetilde{W}_2^{(m, m-1, m-2)*}$ is the conjugate space to the space $\widetilde{W}_2^{(m, m-1, m-2)}$ and the conjugate space consists of all periodic functionals which are orthogonal to the unity [11], i.e.,

$$(\ell, 1) = 0 \quad (6)$$

Simplifying the right-hand side of the above equality and taking into account the condition (6) we obtain the following analytical expression

$$\|\ell\|_{\widetilde{W}_2^{(m, m-1, m-2)}} = (-1)^m \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{k'=1}^N C_k C_{k'} \sum_{\beta \neq 0} \frac{e^{-2\pi i \beta (hk - hk')}}{((2\pi i \beta)^m - (2\pi i \beta)^{m-2})^2}$$

Conclusion

This paper has addressed the problem of estimating the upper bound of the absolute error for an optimal quadrature formula in the space of real-valued periodic functions. The analysis is based on the use of the extremal function associated with the quadrature formula, which allows for an effective evaluation of the error. It is shown that the norm of the error functional for the optimal quadrature formula constructed in this space is smaller than the corresponding norm in the Sobolev space. These results demonstrate the advantage of the proposed approach for numerical integration of periodic functions. Future research will focus on a deeper investigation of the error functional, including the explicit computation of its norm and the determination of the optimal coefficients of the quadrature formula, with the aim of further improving the accuracy and efficiency of optimal quadrature methods.

References:

1. Sobolev S. L., Vaskevich V. L. The Theory of Cubature Formulas. Dor-drecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers Group, 1997.
2. Iserles A., Nrsett S. P. Efficient quadrature of highly oscillatory integrals using

- derivatives, Proc. R. Soc. A, 2005. vol. 461, pp. 1383-1399.
3. Boltaev A. K., Shadimetov Kh. M., Nuraliev F. A. The extremal function of interpolation formulas in $W(2,0)$ 2 space, Vestnik KRAUNC. Fiz.-Mat. nauki, 2021. vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 123- 132.
 4. Filon L. N. G. On a quadrature formula for trigonometric integrals, Proc. Roy. Soc., 1928. vol. 49, pp. 38-47.
 - 5 Shadimetov Kh. M. Optimal lattice quadrature and cubature formulas in Sobolev spaces. Tashkent: Fan, 2019 (In Russian).
 6. Demidenko G. V., Vaskevich V. L. Selected Works of S. L. Sobolev. New York: Springer, 2006. 603 pp.
 7. Hayotov A. R., Jeon S., Shadimetov Kh. M. Application of optimal quadrature formulas for reconstruction of CT images, Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics, 2021. vol. 388, pp. 113313.
 8. Milovanović G. V., Stanić M. P. Numerical Integration of Highly Oscillating Functions / Analytic Number Theory, Approximation Theory and Special Functions. Berlin, Springer, 2014, pp. 613-649.
 9. Nikolskii S. M. Quadrature formulas. Moscow: Nauka, 1988 (In Russian).
 10. Shadimetov Kh. M. , Azamov S.S., Kobilov H.M Optimization of Approximate Integration Formulas for Periodic Function Classes, Problems of Computational and Applied Mathematics, 2025. Vol(3) , 116, pp.
 11. Sard A. Best approximate integration formulas; best approximation formulas, Amer. J. Math., 1949. vol. 71, pp. 80-91.

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 10.01.2026-yil.
Bichimi 70x100 1/16, "Times New Roman"
garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.